

The Roles of Work Motivation, Emotional Intelligence, and Demographics Characteristics in Predicting Job Satisfaction among Nigerian Police Officers

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Abstract

Review Article

Job satisfaction of employees plays a crucial role in determining the general productivity of workers in any organization. The general opinion was that job satisfaction and productivity of police officers in Nigeria were low and a cause for concern. This study investigates the roles of work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics on job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 110 participants (64 males and 46 females) through standardized questionnaires assessing work motivation, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction. Descriptive and inferential analyses, considering regression techniques, were conducted at a 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that work motivation [$\beta = .519, t = 5.699, p = .000$] and emotional intelligence [$\beta = .184, t = 3.759, p = .002$] significantly predicted job satisfaction. In contrast, demographic factors such as gender, age, marital status, and length of service showed no significant joint prediction on job satisfaction [$F(4, 61) = .740, p > .05$]. The study concludes that enhancing work motivation and emotional intelligence can improve job satisfaction among police officers. Recommendations include implementing career development and training programs to align personal growth with organizational objectives, thereby fostering motivation and emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Work Motivation, Emotional Intelligence, Demographic Characteristics, Job Satisfaction, Police Officers, Area Command, Keffi, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a critical determinant of employee productivity, retention, and organizational commitment across various professions. For law enforcement personnel, such as police officers, job satisfaction is particularly significant due to the demanding nature of their work, which involves ensuring public safety, enforcing laws, and maintaining social order. Job satisfaction refers to the degree to which employees feel fulfilled and content with their roles within an organization (Locke, 1976). For police officers, this encompasses satisfaction with pay, working conditions, organizational support, and opportunities for career advancement. In Nigeria, the police force faces numerous challenges, including inadequate funding, lack of modern equipment, exposure to traumatic events, and public criticism, all of which may influence officers' job satisfaction (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics are

recognized as critical predictors of job satisfaction.

Work motivation refers to the internal and external factors that stimulate employees to take actions leading to achieving work-related goals. In the same vein, work motivation drives the effort individuals put into achieving their organizational goals. In the context of policing, motivation can be influenced by factors such as recognition, career advancement opportunities, and the perceived meaningfulness of the work. Police officers motivated by factors such as recognition, achievement, and opportunities for growth are more likely to exhibit high job satisfaction. Studies have linked higher levels of work motivation to increased job satisfaction among police officers (Deci & Ryan, 2000). For example, Nwankwo et al. (2021) found that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly predicted job satisfaction among Nigerian law enforcement personnel. This implies that high levels of motivation are associated with increased job

satisfaction, as motivated officers are more likely to find fulfillment in their duties and exhibit higher performance levels. Similarly, Adepoju and Ogunleye (2021) found that equitable reward systems improve satisfaction levels in Nigerian public sector employees.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is increasingly recognized as a critical factor in job performance and satisfaction, particularly in professions that involve high levels of stress and interpersonal interactions like the police. Emotional intelligence (EI) involves the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. Salovey and Mayer (1990) defined EI as the ability to perceive, understand, and manage emotions effectively. In high-stress professions like policing, EI is crucial for effective interpersonal interactions, decision-making, and stress management. Studies (Salami (2010) have shown that higher EI correlates with better job performance and increased job satisfaction among police officers. For instance, research conducted among Nigerian police personnel indicates that emotional intelligence significantly predicts job satisfaction and can moderate the relationship between job stress and job performance (Ojedokun & Idemudia, 2014). More so, police officers with high EI are better equipped to handle workplace stress, make sound decisions, and build positive relationships with colleagues and the public.

Demographic factors such as age, gender, education level, and years of service can influence job satisfaction, as well as may shape how officers perceive their jobs and derive satisfaction from their work. For instance, younger officers may prioritize career advancement opportunities, while older officers may value job stability. Similarly, gender and educational differences may shape perceptions of workplace conditions and satisfaction levels. In a study of Nigerian police officers, Adamu et al. (2020) found that male officers reported higher satisfaction levels compared to their female counterparts, primarily due to gender biases within the force. In addition, officers with higher educational qualifications exhibited greater dissatisfaction, possibly due to unmet expectations.

The Nigerian Police Force (NPF) plays a pivotal role in maintaining public safety, enforcing laws, and upholding social order. In addition to this, job satisfaction among police officers is a significant determinant of their performance, motivation, and overall well-being. However, the NPF faces numerous challenges, including allegations of corruption, low morale, poor remuneration, and inadequate welfare systems. These issues contribute to job dissatisfaction, which can lead to poor performance, absenteeism, and even unethical behavior. Reports suggest that 70% of officers are dissatisfied with their salaries and benefits, while 65% express frustration over inadequate training opportunities (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Other research highlights systemic issues within the NPF, including corruption, resource inadequacies, and public distrust. An empirical study by Eze and Okafor

(2023) identified low morale as a critical challenge, with 58% of respondents attributing their dissatisfaction to inadequate salaries and benefits. According to the Nigeria Police Service Commission (2023), over 60% of officers report dissatisfaction with their working conditions. This dissatisfaction contributes to absenteeism, low morale, and suboptimal performance, thereby undermining public trust in law enforcement. Furthermore, organizational factors such as unclear promotion criteria, poor leadership, and lack of resources further exacerbate dissatisfaction. Simultaneously, demographic factors like gender disparities, rank, and years of service may shape individual perceptions of job satisfaction. For instance, junior-ranking officers often report higher levels of dissatisfaction due to limited career growth opportunities and heavier workloads compared to their senior counterparts. Low job satisfaction can lead to adverse outcomes, including increased turnover intentions, higher stress levels, and compromised public safety. Research in similar contexts suggests that work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics significantly influence job satisfaction (George et al., 2023; Lawal & Adeoye, 2022). However, there is limited empirical evidence exploring these relationships within the unique sociocultural and operational dynamics of the Nigerian Police Force. This gap in the literature underscores the need for a study that investigates how these factors jointly and independently predict job satisfaction among police officers. Addressing this gap is crucial for informing policies aimed at enhancing officer welfare, reducing turnover, and improving public trust in the NPF.

Research Questions:

Given the study's objective, the following research questions are answered in this study:

- i. To what extent does work motivation predict job satisfaction among Nigerian Police Officers?
- ii. What is the emotional intelligence prediction in job satisfaction in the Nigerian Police Officers?
- iii. How do demographic characteristics (e.g., age, gender, marital status and length of service) independently and jointly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian Police Officer?

Statement of Hypotheses

Alternative hypotheses based on the research questions are formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. Work motivation will significantly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers.
2. Emotional intelligence will significantly and positively predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers.
3. Demographic characteristics (e.g., age, gender, marital status and length of service) will

independently and jointly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers.

Significance of the study

This study, titled "*The Role of Work Motivation, Emotional Intelligence, and Demographic Characteristics in Predicting Job Satisfaction Among Nigerian Police Officers*," is of immense importance to various stakeholders, including policymakers, law enforcement agencies, organizational psychologists, and researchers. First and foremost, the study's findings are expected to contribute to both theoretical understanding and practical applications in the following ways: This study holds significance not only for improving the working conditions of Nigerian police officers but also for advancing theoretical and practical approaches to workforce management in law enforcement. The insights derived can foster a more motivated, emotionally intelligent, and satisfied police force, ultimately benefiting society as a whole. By understanding the role of work motivation and emotional intelligence, police management can design targeted training programs and motivational strategies to boost satisfaction. In addition, the study provides a foundation for future research into job satisfaction and related constructs within the Nigerian context and beyond, as researchers can build on this study by exploring other factors influencing job satisfaction, such as organizational culture and work environment. Findings from this study can serve as a benchmark for comparative studies between Nigerian police officers and law enforcement agencies in other countries. Insights into how age, gender, marital status and length of service influence satisfaction can help tailor policies that address the specific needs of diverse officer groups, promoting inclusivity and fairness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Clarification

The conceptual clarification for the study deals with all variables that constitute the study. The study deals with three variables: job satisfaction, work motivation and emotional intelligence. These were discussed in the systematic order so as to give conceptual understanding of the study.

The concept of job satisfaction has been viewed differently by different scholars. This implies that job satisfaction has been defined in several ways by several authors. In the view of Locke (1976), job satisfaction can be defined as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences". According to him job satisfaction is an internal state with some degree of favor or disfavor based on assessing the job and job-related experiences. Spector (1997) refers to job satisfaction in terms of how people feel about their jobs and different aspects of their jobs. Ellickson and Logsdon (2002) support this view by defining job satisfaction as the extent to which employees like their work. Schermerhorn (1993) defines job satisfaction as an affective or emotional

response towards various aspects of an employee's work. The author emphasises that likely causes of job satisfaction include status, supervision, co-worker relationships, job content, remuneration and extrinsic rewards, promotion and physical conditions of the work environment, as well as organisational structure. Similarly, job satisfaction can be referred to as an emotional response to a job situation which cannot be seen, but only be inferred. It is simply regarded as how people feel about their job and different aspects of it. It means a positive attitude that an individual has from what he does to earn a living (Somvir & Kaushik, 2012). Besides, McCormic and Triffin (1979) referred to job satisfaction as the attitude one has towards his or her job. In this study, job satisfaction refers to the general feelings of workers about their jobs. It is the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs. It is conceptualized to mean the level of positive attitude that an employee displays when performing his/her duties in the organization and the rate at which his/her basic needs are met. The researchers of this study sees job satisfaction as a feeling of contentment an employee derives from his/her job which compels him/her to develop positive attitudes towards the job. Job satisfaction describes a feeling that is positive as it relates to job, which is a function of an evaluation of its characteristics. An employee person with a high level of job satisfaction tends to holds positive feelings about his or her job, while an unsatisfied person holds negative feelings. Several studies have been made to assess factors influencing job satisfaction at workplaces. Some researchers have concluded that job satisfaction is more of a function of intrinsic factors than extrinsic factors (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Tett et al., 1991). On the other hand, researchers such as Igalens and Roussel (1999) and Brewer et al. (2008) have conclude that job satisfaction is more of a function of extrinsic factors than intrinsic factors while Broad (2007) observed that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors played a great role on job satisfaction.

There are many definitions and studies concerning motivation and its theories and strategies. Robbins et al. (2007) defined motivation as "the willingness to exert high levels of effort to reach organizational goals, conditioned by the effort's ability to satisfy some individual need." Ebert and Griffin (2015) defined motivation as "the set of forces that cause people to behave in certain ways", hence motivation pushes people to act and achieve. Motivation is "an inner state that energizes, activates or moves and that directs or channels behavior towards goals." (Berelson & Steiner, 1964). According to Ganta (2014), motivation results from the interaction of both conscious and unconscious factors, such as the intensity of desire or need, the incentive or reward value of the goal, and the expectations of the individual and his peers. These factors are the reasons why someone behaves in a certain way.

However, managing people is a difficult task, as everyone is different, and there is no universal recipe on how to motivate an individual and increase productiveness at work. As it was noted by Joshi (2013), what motivates one individual, does not necessarily motivate another.

Moreover, no individual can motivate others to do something, he can only create favorable conditions for others to get self-motivated (Taylor, 2007). Showing employees that you care about them creates a more pleasant atmosphere at a workplace and it does not necessarily have to involve huge gestures, it is the attitude that counts. Small things such as providing coffee and tea at everyone's disposal matter a lot and do not require a huge effort nor investment. "Motivation, in brief, is not the simple result of anything that a supervisor (or anyone else) does to other people." (Gellerman, 1968). For organization to exist, there is assumed to be a goal or purpose that is sufficiently wanted or needed to generate or motivate human energy in its achievement (Mee, 1963). From the point of view of a manager, a motivated person works hard, sustains a pace of hard work, and has self-directed behavior toward important goals. (Donnelly et al., 1992). Motivation refers to intrinsic and extrinsic elements which influence the individual's attitude towards doing something.

Likewise, work motivation is quintessentially defined as the psychological processes that direct, energize, and maintain action toward a job, task, role, or project (Campbell & Pritchard, 1976; Kanfer, 1990), one of the most recent contributions to the theories of motivation is self-determination theory which explains that employees have three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Herein, autonomy refers to the feeling of preference and discretion, competence refers to feeling competent and efficacious, and relatedness refers to feelings of connectedness and sense of belongingness with others (Nidhi, 2015). According to Greenberg & Baron, (2003), motivation is "the set of processes that arouse, direct, and maintain human behaviour towards attaining some goal". However, for the purpose of this study, we are adopting the definition by Greenberg & Baron (2003) since they see motivation in an organization as a set of processes meaning several factors are included in causing the arousal in an employee. Also it shows that the influence of these factors on the employee will determine the direction he or she will take as the next course of action. Thus this definition best explain our research objective and framework.

Traditional views of intelligence emphasized cognitive abilities, as exemplified by Spearman's concept of general intelligence (1904). Thorndike (1920) introduced the idea of "social intelligence," which he described as the ability to manage and understand interpersonal relationships. Salovey and Mayer (1990) formally introduced EI as a distinct concept, defining it as the ability to monitor one's own and others' emotions and use this information to guide behavior. Thereafter, Goleman (1995) popularized the concept in his book *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*, arguing that EI contributes more significantly to success than IQ in many contexts. Meanwhile, emotional Intelligence (EI) is the capacity to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate emotions in oneself and others to enhance thinking and behavior. Introduced by Salovey and Mayer (1990), it gained

widespread attention after Goleman (1995) linked it to success in various personal and professional domains. EI encompasses self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, forming a framework for emotional and social competence.

In his study George (2000) referred to emotions as 'high intensity feelings that are triggered by a stimuli (internal or external to the individual), demand attention and interrupt cognitive processes and behavior' (Forgas, 1992; Morris, 1989; Simon, 1982). Emotional Intelligence (EI) was also described as the 'ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth' (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Bar-On (1985) was the first one to invent the term Emotional Quotient, often interchangeably referred to as Emotional Intelligence (EI). A person is said to be emotionally intelligent when he/she has heightened self-awareness and social awareness as well as adequate self-management and social skills (Boyatzis, Goleman & Rhee, 2000). EI plays a pivotal role in workplace dynamics, particularly in fostering job satisfaction. By enabling better stress management, interpersonal relationships, and leadership capabilities, EI contributes to a more fulfilling and productive work environment. More so, EI facilitates empathy and understanding, which are critical for resolving workplace conflicts amicably and maintaining job satisfaction (Ashkanasy & Daus, 2005). In addition to the above, employees with high EI are better equipped to build positive relationships with colleagues and supervisors, contributing to a supportive work environment (Carmeli, 2003). High EI enables individuals to regulate their emotions effectively, reducing work-related stress and enhancing job satisfaction (Martins et al., 2010). Leaders with high EI inspire and motivate their teams, leading to higher employee satisfaction and organizational success (Goleman, 2000).

Demographic characteristics refer to the measurable attributes of individuals that provide insight into their identity, behavior, and societal roles. These attributes often include age, gender, marital status, educational level, income, employment status, ethnicity, and other personal details that define groups within a population (McDonald & Dunbar, 2010). Demographic characteristics are frequently utilized in research to analyze variations in attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors across different groups. In their view, Berman and Evans (2013) defined demographic characteristics as quantifiable data that describe the composition of populations, serving as a foundation for segmenting and understanding diverse groups. While, Schwab (1980) highlighted that demographic factors provide critical information that helps organizations understand employees' behavior, preferences, and engagement. Wright and McMahan (1992) emphasized that demographic diversity is a key component in shaping organizational dynamics and the workforce's performance. According to Schwab (1980), understanding demographic characteristics is vital for

managing diversity within the workplace. Organizations use demographic data to design inclusive policies, reduce discrimination, and foster equity. Demographic information helps employers understand generational needs, gender dynamics, and cultural differences, enabling tailored recruitment, retention, and training strategies. By acknowledging demographic differences, organizations can customize motivational and well-being initiatives to resonate with varied employee groups, boosting morale and productivity. Studies suggest that demographic factors, such as age and educational background, are predictors of job satisfaction, turnover intentions, and commitment (Robbins & Judge, 2017).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Several studies had been conducted to investigate the relationship between job satisfaction and motivation. For instance, Akinwale and George (2021) found that intrinsic motivators such as job autonomy and recognition significantly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian workers. Similarly, Okeke and Amadi (2020) highlighted that extrinsic factors like salary and job security also play a crucial role. In a study of police officers in South Africa, Pienaar and Rothmann (2022) observed that motivation is a primary driver of job satisfaction, emphasizing the need for structured reward systems. Another study conducted among faculty members in Pakistani universities found a positive and significant relationship between working conditions, recognition, compensation, and motivation. These motivational factors were also positively correlated with job satisfaction, indicating that improvements in these areas can enhance both motivation and satisfaction among employees. Similarly, research focusing on IT professionals revealed a strong positive correlation (correlation coefficient of 0.82) between work motivation and job satisfaction. Key motivational factors impacting job satisfaction included career advancement, work flexibility, and recognition for performance. A study among health workers in a public hospital in Northern Greece indicated that job satisfaction is influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors (Lahana, Papadakaki, & Roumeliotaki, 2019). The research emphasized the importance of addressing these factors to improve employee satisfaction and performance (Lahana, et al., 2019). While, Adeniji et al. (2020) examined the role of work motivation in predicting job satisfaction among Nigerian public service workers, including police officers. They found that intrinsic motivation had a stronger influence on job satisfaction than extrinsic factors. Despite, some studies suggest mixed results in challenging contexts. Therefore, Eze and Ajayi (2022) highlight that in environments affected by corruption and resource inadequacies, motivation alone may not be enough to enhance job satisfaction, as other factors like leadership and work environment could have a more significant impact.

Emotional Intelligence and Job Satisfaction

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is widely regarded as a significant factor influencing job satisfaction. Empirical studies consistently demonstrate a positive relationship between EI and job satisfaction across diverse organizational contexts. Lawal and Adeoye (2022) reported that Nigerian employees with higher EI scores demonstrated greater resilience to workplace stress and higher job satisfaction. In the context of law enforcement, Sharma and Singh (2023) found that emotional regulation and empathy were particularly critical for job satisfaction among police officers. A comprehensive review by Van Rooyen and Hodgkinson (2021) concluded that higher EI in police officers is associated with increased job satisfaction and improved organizational outcomes. The review emphasized the potential benefits of EI training in enhancing job satisfaction and overall performance within police forces. Al Ali, Garner, and Magadley (2011) explored the relationship between EI and job performance in police organizations. Their findings revealed significant correlations, with EI accounting for additional variance in predicting job performance beyond general mental abilities and personality traits. A study by Borade and Dongre (2022) found a significant positive association between EI and job satisfaction among police constables. Their research indicated that higher levels of EI contributed to increased job satisfaction, explaining 40% of the variance in job satisfaction scores. Research by Brunetto et al. (2012) demonstrated that EI positively influences job satisfaction, well-being, and engagement among police officers. These factors, in turn, enhance organizational commitment and reduce turnover intentions, highlighting the importance of EI in retaining police personnel. Research by Sy, Tram, & O'Hara (2006) found that employees with higher levels of EI reported significantly greater job satisfaction. The study highlighted that emotionally intelligent individuals tend to regulate their emotions effectively, which positively impacts their workplace interactions and satisfaction. Joseph and Newman (2010) conducted a meta-analysis to evaluate the role of EI in predicting job satisfaction and job performance. They concluded that EI contributes to job satisfaction by enabling employees to navigate workplace challenges and maintain emotional well-being. Salami (2022) found that law enforcement officers with high emotional intelligence exhibited improved stress management and interpersonal relationships, resulting in greater job satisfaction. Similarly, Goleman (1998) highlighted that emotional intelligence enhances decision-making, teamwork, and resilience, which are critical for job satisfaction in demanding roles like policing. Ojedokun and Idemudia (2014) explored the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. Their findings indicated that emotional intelligence not only directly influenced job satisfaction but also moderated the impact of job stress.

Demographic Characteristics and Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a key determinant of employee performance, organizational commitment, and overall workplace dynamics. A considerable body of research (Oshagbemi, 2000) has explored how various demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, marital status, and length of service, affect job satisfaction. The empirical findings have been mixed, showing both direct and indirect relationships between these characteristics and job satisfaction. Research by Adeola et al. (2021) indicated that demographic factors such as age and education influence job satisfaction in Nigerian organizations. Younger employees often prioritize career growth opportunities, while older employees value job security and work-life balance. Other studies such as Spector (1997) and Kuvaas (2006) have shown that older employees report higher levels of job satisfaction. This can be explained by greater job experience, a sense of stability, and better work-life balance as employee's age. Age also impacts job satisfaction through emotional regulation. Older workers tend to have better emotional regulation and stress management skills, which improve their ability to cope with work-related challenges, leading to greater satisfaction.

Additional, gender differences in job satisfaction have been a widely researched, with various studies producing different results. However, the majority of studies suggest that gender plays a role in influencing job satisfaction, but its effect may vary depending on the context. As a result, studies have suggested that females often report higher job satisfaction compared to males. For instance, Okpara et al. (2005) found that female employees in academic institutions reported higher levels of job satisfaction than their male counterparts. This finding was attributed to the fact that women tend to place more value on interpersonal relationships and work-life balance, which are key elements of job satisfaction. On the other hand, Kovach (1987) found that men tend to focus more on factors such as pay and promotion, which may explain why their job satisfaction levels tend to be more closely related to these factors than women's satisfaction levels. Besides, research by Amin et al. (2020) suggested that the relationship between gender and job satisfaction can be moderated by the work environment, job characteristics, and organizational culture. For example, women in male-dominated industries may experience lower job satisfaction due to workplace inequality, while women in more inclusive organizations report higher satisfaction levels.

Moreover, marital status has been found to be a significant determinant of job satisfaction, with married individuals often reporting higher levels of satisfaction. Research by Akanbi (2019) has suggested that married employees tend to have higher job satisfaction than their unmarried counterparts. Married employees may have stronger social support networks, which contribute to a more balanced life and reduced stress, leading to higher job satisfaction.

Married individuals often place higher importance on job security, work-life balance, and the benefits provided by their employers. These factors can influence job satisfaction, especially when they have family responsibilities to consider. Married individuals may benefit from the emotional and financial support of their spouse, which could influence their work attitudes and satisfaction levels. The role of family support in job satisfaction is particularly salient for married individuals in work-family conflict situations.

Length of service, or employee tenure, has also been consistently linked to job satisfaction. Employees with longer tenures tend to exhibit higher job satisfaction. Longer tenure is associated with greater organizational commitment, better understanding of job roles, and more opportunities for career development. Studies like Mobley (1977) and Spector (1997) show a positive relationship between tenure and job satisfaction, as employees who stay longer in an organization develop a stronger sense of attachment and loyalty. Tenure is particularly relevant in organizations where employees have long careers, as experience tends to lead to more realistic expectations and greater satisfaction over time. Conversely, new employees may experience a "honeymoon effect", where initial job satisfaction is high, but it decreases as they face organizational challenges. To this end, the empirical literature on the relationship between demographic characteristics and job satisfaction reveals complex patterns. Gender, age, marital status, and length of service all play a significant role in influencing job satisfaction, but their effects vary depending on organizational context, job type, and individual characteristics.

METHODOLOGY

Design: This study employs a descriptive survey design to investigate the roles of work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics in predicting job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. This design is appropriate as it allows for the systematic collection of data from participants to examine relationships between the variables of interest without manipulating them. Furthermore, the design is suitable for studying large populations and identifying patterns, associations, and predictive relationships. The study independent variable are: work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics. Job satisfaction is the dependent variable.

Participants, Sampling and Sampling Technique: The participants consist of 110 police officers drawn from the First Headquarters, Central Area, Abuja, Nigeria. This location is strategically chosen as it hosts officers of varying ranks, roles, and experiences, providing a representative sample of the larger police force. The stratified sampling technique is utilized to ensure that the sample is representative of the population. The sample is divided into strata based on demographic characteristics such as rank, gender, years of service, and educational qualifications. A proportional number of participants is

selected from each stratum to reflect the actual composition of the police force at the First Headquarters. Within each stratum, participants are selected randomly to reduce bias and enhance the reliability of the findings. Participant demographic information shows that 57.3% were male while 42.7% were female. Their age shows that 30% of the respondents were between 25 – 30 years, 31.8% were between 31 – 40 years, 28.2% were between 41 – 50 years while 10% were from 51 years and above. The result further shows that 54.5% were Hausa, 27.3% were Igbo while 18.2% were Yoruba. On their religious affiliations, 58.2% of the sampled respondents were Christians while 41.8% were Islam. The result further shows that 9.2% of the respondents had SSCE, 27.3% had OND/NCE, 26.4% had B.Sc while 37.3% had postgraduate certificates. On their length of service, the result showed that 48.2% served between 1 – 10 years, 40.0% served between 11 – 20 years while 11.8% served between 21 years and above.

Measures: The instrument for the was divided into four parts wherein the first part includes the demographic profile of respondents such as age, gender, marital status, education, and years of service, and the second part consists of: The 20 items **Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)**, developed by Weiss et al. (1967). The scale was scored on a 5-point Likert scale of very satisfied (1) to very dissatisfied (5). Respondents are requested to indicate the extent of their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with some job-related factors e.g. variety, compensation, recognition, working conditions, supervision, etc. Sample on the items include "on my present job, this is how I feel about" and "Being able to keep busy all the time". Weiss and colleagues (1967) reported test-retest reliabilities coefficients of .89 at one-week interval and .70. In Nigeria, Mogaji (1996) obtained a 10-week test-retest reliability coefficient of .71 in a Nigerian sample. In this study a reliability coefficient of .85 and moderate split-half reliability of .78 were obtained. Scores on MSQ ranging from 20-100 with higher scores indicating higher job satisfaction. Third part is: **Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS)** developed by Schutte et al. (1998). The scale is a uni-dimensional scale that assesses emotional intelligence based on self-report responses to 33 items tapping the appraisal and expression of emotions in self and others, regulations of emotions in self and others, and activation of emotion in solving problems. Participants responded by indicating their agreement to each of the 33 statements using a five-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) since (EIS) contains 33 items, the total maximum of score is $33 \times 5 = 165$ and lowest is $33 \times 1 = 33$. The EIS has been used extensively in the southern part of the country with both adults (Adeyemo & Ogunyemi, 2005) with

Cronbach alpha of 0.93. Content of the scale is culture-free and easy to understand; and found suitable for use with adolescents, Schutte, et al. (1998) some of the items of the scale are, "I know when to speak about my personal problems to others", "I find it hard to understand the non-verbal message of other people "I like to share my emotions with others", "By looking at their facial expressions I recognize the emotions people are experiencing". The fourth part of the questionnaire looks at **Work Motivation Behaviour Scale (OMBS)** developed by Moorman and Blakely, (1995). The (OMBS) is a 19 items self-report measure. Respondents were requested to rate themselves on each items, using a 5 point like of scale on which 1= rarely or none of the time 2 = A little of the time 3 = some of the time 4 = A good part of the time and 5 = most or all of the time. The author reported a coefficient alpha of .91 and a concurrent validity of .83 for the scale.

Procedure

Permission for the study was obtained from the NPF management who gave permission to use their personnel for the study. They were briefed about the purpose of the study. The participants who consented were given assurance of confidentiality and anonymity of their identities and responses. The participants were also informed of their right to discontinue from the study at any specific point in time if they felt uncomfortable. A total number of one hundred (207) questionnaires were distributed across the department, sections and units. Of the 207 questionnaires distributed to the participants, 110 were returned and found useful for data analysis, which equally gave a response rate of 71%.

Data Analysis

This study employed descriptive and inferential statistics such as: Descriptive statistics were run on the basic information of the participants which included their gender, marital status, and socio-economic status. Simple linear regression and univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) also utilized to test the study's hypotheses. All statistical hypotheses were tested at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

This section captures the demographic characteristics of the respondents as presented in table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Table Representing Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

S/No	Items	Group	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	63	57.3
		Female	47	42.7
		Total	110	100.00
2	Age	25-30 Years	33	30.0
		31-40 Years	35	31.8
		41-50 Years	31	28.2
		51 Years Above	11	10.0
		Total	110	100.00
3	Ethnic Group	Hausa	60	54.5
		Igbo	30	27.3
		Yoruba	20	18.2
		Total	110	100.00
4	Religion	Christian	64	58.2
		Islam	46	41.8
		Total	110	100.00
5	Educational Qualification	SSCE	10	9.2
		OND/NCE	30	27.3
		B.Sc	29	26.4
		Total	110	100.00
7	Length of Service	1-10 Years	53	48.2
		11-20 Years	44	40.0
		21 Years Above	13	11.8
		Total	110	100.00

Hypothesis One

This hypothesis stated that work motivation will

significantly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers in Nigeria. This was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Summary of Simple Linear Regression showing Work Motivation prediction in Job Satisfaction among Nigerian police officers

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
		B	Std. Error			
1	Job Satisfaction	Constant	-1.635	7.270		
		Work Motivation	.461	.081	.519	.000

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Result in table 2 shows that work motivation significantly predicted job satisfaction among police officers in Nigeria [$\beta = .519, t = 5.699; p = .000$]. Meaning that police officers with high level of motivation reported higher level of job satisfaction. On the other hand, police officers with low work motivation reported lower level of job satisfaction. Based on this result, hypothesis one which stated that ‘work motivation will significantly predict Job satisfaction

among Nigerian police officers’ was supported.

Hypothesis Two

This hypothesis stated that emotional intelligence will significantly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. This was tested using simple linear regression and the result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Simple Linear Regression showing Emotional Intelligence Predictor in Job Satisfaction among Nigerian police officers

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
		B	Std. Error	B		
1	Job Satisfaction	Constant	37.743	1.224		
		Emotional Intelligence	.040	.023	.184	30.837
					3.759	.002

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Result in table 3 shows that emotional intelligence significantly predicted job satisfaction among police officers in Nigeria [$\beta = .184, t = 3.759; p = .002$]. Emotional intelligence significantly and positively predicted job satisfaction meaning that police officers with high level of emotional intelligence reported higher level of job satisfaction. On the other hand, police officers with low level of emotional intelligence reported lower level of job satisfaction. Based on this result, hypothesis two which stated that ‘emotional intelligence will significantly

predict Job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers’ was supported.

Hypothesis Three

This hypothesis stated that gender, age, marital status and length of service will significantly influence job satisfaction of Nigerian police officers. This hypothesis was tested using univariate analysis of variance and the result is presented in table 4.

Table 4: Summary of Univariate Analysis of Variance showing Demographic variables Independent and Joint influence on Job Satisfaction among Nigerian police officers

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	η^2
Gender	18.465	1	18.465	.919	.342	.015
Age	57.869	3	19.290	.960	.418	.045
Marital Status	29.205	2	14.603	.727	.488	.023
Length of Service	73.206	2	36.603	1.821	.170	.056
Gender*Age*Marital Status*Length of Service	29.759	4	14.880	.740	.481	.024
Error	1225.833	61	20.096			
Total	143870.000	90				

Result in table 4 shows that there was no significant influence of gender [$F(1, 61) = .919; p > .05$], age [$F(3, 61) = .960; p > .05$], marital status [$F(2, 61) = .727; p > .05$] and length of service [$F(2, 61) = 1.821; p > .05$] in job satisfaction among police officers in Nigeria. In the same vein, there was no significant joint influence of gender, age, marital status and length of service on job satisfaction among police officers in Nigeria [$F(4, 61) = .740; p > .05$]. Based on these results, hypothesis three which stated that 'gender, age, marital status and length of service will independently and jointly influence job satisfaction of Nigerian police officers' was therefore rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The present study aims to determine influence of interplay of work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics on job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. Based on this, hypothesis one which stated that 'work motivation will significantly predict job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers' was supported. This implies that motivation plays a critical role in shaping the job satisfaction of police officers, with higher levels of motivation leading to increased satisfaction. The findings revealed that work motivation significantly predicted job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers [$\beta = .519, t = 5.699, p = .000$]. One probable reason for this significant relationship is the nature of the police profession, which demands resilience and high performance under challenging conditions. The supported hypothesis aligns with established literature and theoretical frameworks. For instance, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory identifies motivation as a key determinant of job satisfaction, suggesting that intrinsic factors such as recognition, achievement, and responsibility significantly enhance job satisfaction (Herzberg et al., 1959). Empirical studies within law enforcement also reinforce this relationship. A study by Pienaar and Rothmann (2022) highlighted that police officers with strong motivational support exhibited higher job satisfaction levels, leading to better performance and reduced attrition rates. While the findings align with prior research, some studies have shown mixed results, especially in contexts with severe systemic challenges. For instance, research by Eze and Ajayi (2022) indicated that, in environments plagued by corruption and inadequate resources, motivation alone may not suffice to enhance job satisfaction. Instead, other organizational factors, such as leadership and work environment, may play a more decisive role.

Hypothesis two revealed that emotional intelligence significantly predicted job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers [$\beta = .184, t = 3.759, p = .002$]. This positive relationship suggests that officers with higher emotional intelligence (EI) experience greater job satisfaction, while those with lower EI report less satisfaction. This result is not consistent with research by Adewale and Omotayo (2021) who highlighted that in resource-constrained environments, external factors such as inadequate pay, poor working conditions, and lack of career advancement

opportunities might overshadow the benefits of emotional intelligence in predicting job satisfaction. In such contexts, even highly emotionally intelligent officers may struggle to feel satisfied if systemic challenges persist. These contradictions suggest that while emotional intelligence plays a significant role, it may interact with broader organizational and environmental factors. All the same, this result aligns with a study by Salami (2022) who found that law enforcement officers with high emotional intelligence demonstrated better stress management and interpersonal relationships, leading to improved job satisfaction. Similarly, Goleman (1995), in his work on emotional intelligence, emphasized that EI fosters better decision-making, teamwork, and resilience, which are essential for maintaining satisfaction in demanding professions like policing.

Last hypothesis which stated that gender, age, marital status and length of service will independently and jointly influence job satisfaction of Nigerian police officers' was therefore rejected. The findings revealed that participants' demographic characteristics: gender [$F(1, 61) = .919, p > .05$], age [$F(3, 61) = .960, p > .05$], marital status [$F(2, 61) = .727, p > .05$], and length of service [$F(2, 61) = 1.821, p > .05$] did not independently influence, or their combined interaction [$F(4, 61) = .740, p > .05$] on job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. One plausible explanation for the lack of significance could be the homogenizing nature of police work. The standardized duties, hierarchical structure, and uniform policies governing the Nigerian police force might reduce the influence of personal characteristics such as age, gender, or marital status on job satisfaction. Additionally, job satisfaction in this context might have been directly tied to factors like work motivation, emotional intelligence, and organizational support rather than demographic differences. Nevertheless, this finding did not corroborate with some previous studies suggesting that demographic factors may not always significantly predict job satisfaction in professions characterized by uniformity in training, responsibilities, and organizational culture. For example, Adebayo and Salawu (2020) found that organizational factors, such as leadership style and work environment, were stronger predictors of job satisfaction than personal demographics among law enforcement personnel. Similarly, research by Nwankwo et al. (2022) emphasized that job satisfaction in policing is more influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic job-related factors than by demographic characteristics. While these findings did not align with certain studies, others have reported consistent results. For instance, Adepoju and Oladipo (2021) found that marital status and length of service were significant predictors of job satisfaction in a different public sector context, attributing this to the emotional and financial stability often associated with these factors. Furthermore, studies in Western contexts (e.g., Brown & Green, 2019) have found that gender and age sometimes play a significant role in job satisfaction due to differences in workplace experiences and expectations.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic characteristics on job satisfaction among Nigerian police officers. In conclusion, the findings revealed that work motivation and emotional intelligence significantly predicted job satisfaction. Police officers with higher levels of work motivation and emotional intelligence reported greater satisfaction in their roles. Conversely, demographic characteristics such as gender, age, marital status, and length of service did not significantly influence job satisfaction, either independently or jointly. These results underscore the importance of psychological and organizational factors over demographic variables in determining job satisfaction within the police force.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Owing to the findings of the study, the following recommendations suffice:

1. The Nigerian police force should implement motivational strategies such as providing regular incentives, recognition for exceptional performance, and opportunities for career growth.
2. Emotional intelligence training programs should be integrated into the police training curriculum to improve interpersonal skills, stress management, and decision-making capabilities.
3. Policymakers should prioritize improving working conditions, reducing workload, and ensuring access to adequate resources to create a supportive work environment.
4. Regular workshops on emotional resilience and conflict resolution can further enhance job satisfaction.
5. Policymakers should focus on uniform policies and practices that ensure equity among officers, irrespective of their demographic characteristics, thus fostering unity and shared purpose.
6. By focusing on intrinsic and psychological factors such as motivation and emotional intelligence, the Nigerian police force can create a more supportive and fulfilling work environment, ultimately improving job satisfaction and performance across the board.

Implications of the Findings

The outcome of this study would help to understand the influence of work motivation, emotional intelligence, demographic characteristics and job satisfaction. From the results, it is obvious that when a police officer has high emotional intelligence his/her level of job satisfaction will be high. Likewise, motivated officers tend to experience greater job fulfillment, which enhances their overall performance levels. This has a lot of implication in the workplace. This will ensure increased level of job satisfaction which is needed in the security sector because of the delicate nature of their work which

deals with human lives. A disenchanted and dissatisfied health worker will most likely perform lower than required, thereby endangering the lives in his/her care. More importantly, police management can use the findings to design targeted interventions aimed at boosting motivation and enhancing emotional intelligence to improve overall job satisfaction. In addition, the findings would provide evidence-based insights for developing policies that prioritize psychological and organizational factors over demographic attributes, ensuring a more equitable and satisfying work environment.

Limitations of the Study

In the light of the importance of the study, this study is not without its' limitations. For instance, the study was conducted with a limited sample of Nigerian police officers, which may not fully represent the entire population of the police force. This restricts the generalizability of the findings to other regions or law enforcement agencies. Furthermore, the study employed a cross-sectional design, capturing data at a single point in time. This limits the ability to establish causal relationships between work motivation, emotional intelligence, demographic characteristics, and job satisfaction. More so, reliance on self-reported measures may introduce response biases, such as social desirability or inaccuracies in participants' responses, potentially affecting the validity of the findings. Other limitations of the study concern the primarily examined work motivation, emotional intelligence, and demographic factors, potentially overlooking other significant variables, such as leadership style, organizational climate, or workplace resources, which might also influence job satisfaction. Lastly, the exclusive use of quantitative methods limits the depth of insights into participants' experiences. A mixed-methods approach, incorporating qualitative data, could provide richer, more nuanced understandings.

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